

Title: Industrial Robots are helping hands not a job taker

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INTRODUCTION:

Robots are of different types and varieties based on its kind, structure and work. Among them Industrial Robots are vastly used in Medical, Car Manufacturing plant, Foundry etc. Industrial Robots performs a dull, dirty and dangerous job in order to ensure workman's health and safety and to increase accuracy which in turn increases productivity. It is a slave which works for the human and doesn't replace the human.

INDUSTRIAL ROBOTS:

Industrial Robots are comprised of 3 or more Degrees of Freedom (DOF), which makes it to move around. Commonly used industrial robots are articulated 6-DOF, which is also called as manipulator or robotic arm. These robots are automated, reprogrammable, reliable and suitable for the operating environment. These are mainly used in machine tending, painting, deburring, sealant dispensing, drilling, welding etc.

BENEFITS:

Following are the benefits yielded from the industrial robot.

1. Repeatability, it works continuously without any break / vacation (excluding the downtime for maintenance and programming)
2. Accurate, very less defects which increases the productivity and profit
3. General-purpose, same robot can be used for welding as well as machine tending
4. Integration, it can communicate with other machines, PC etc.
5. Reprogrammable, can be programmed to do lots of variants and applications.
6. Flexibility, it can move anywhere in its workspace with ease.

ROBOT IS NOT A JOB EATER:

Robot is a machine with little intelligence which comes into existence for making things easy. Robots work in highly hazardous places where human can't work for long period. One of them is Foundry where the temperature rises up to 50°C and exposed to chemicals like zinc, Sulphur, aluminum. Exposure to high temperature and chemicals leads to lung cancer, asthma, reduction in blood cells, hair loss etc. This is the situation where actually necessity of robots come into picture, the robot can continue working in such a situation with periodic maintenance and monitoring is required.

In this scenario, the person who was working in the foundry is replaced by robot and given the job for monitoring the robot, programming robot for different jobs/application or servicing the robot. This has created a new job and relieves the person from hazardous working conditions. Using of Robot for luxury like cleaning the room, folding clothes, cooking, serving, driving is a good innovation but it takes the jobs of few and it makes the human lazy which will eventually overtake the duties.

CONCLUSIONS:

Robots are used in highly hazardous and monotonous work environment under/with the control of technical experts.

KEYWORDS:

Robots, DOF, Jobs

BIOGRAPHY:

GANESAMANIAN. K is a Robotics Passionist, good at programming the robot, has pursued his Bachelor's Degree in Robotics and Automation from PSG College of Technology, INDIA. Currently he is working as a Robotics Engineer in R&D for TAL Manufacturing Solutions, A TATA Enterprise, INDIA since September, and 2016. During this span he has done an innovative project where ATM machine controls the Robot for the firm named as DIEBOLD NIXDORF.